

FEATURES OF RUSSIAN HEALTHCARE DIGITALIZATION

¹Olga Lomovceva, ²Svetlana Soboleva, ³Alexandr Sobolev

¹Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor, Institute of Economics, Management and Law, Moscow City Pedagogical University, Moscow, Russia

²Candidate of Economic Sciences (CSc), Head of Economics and Management Department, Volgograd State Medical University

³Candidate of Economic Sciences (CSc), associate professor Economics and Management Department, Volgograd State Medical University

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to determine the main directions of development of digitalization of the Russian healthcare system, its features, priorities, risks and main historical stages. The study was conducted using industry statistics and analytical materials obtained from official sources, as well as publications in Russian and foreign scientific literature. The study identified areas of improvement with the further expansion of digitalization. Most of them are related to artificial intelligence training systems and the quality of medical data for its training.*

Keywords: *Digital medicine, system implementation of digital technologies, artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, Internet of medical things, telemedicine.*

JEL Classification: I15, I00, J01

1. Introduction

In the context of accelerated technological progress in most developed and developing countries, one of the main priorities for the economic development relating to both social and business goals lies in the field of digitalization of all spheres of society's life (Tukhtabaev et al. 2024). The healthcare sector is no exception in all countries of the world. A general global trend is the need for widespread implementation of information technologies to improve the quality of medical services and improve the management system (Babkin et al. 2023). It is believed that progress in digital healthcare will make it possible to change traditional approaches to medical care, bringing healthcare closer to the needs and requirements of the population, as well as improving the quality of medical services through the digitalization of clinical processes and the introduction of artificial intelligence in management decision-making (Kasimov et al. 2024).

2. Results

In Russia despite the general positive perception of the prospects for the development of medical information systems and their use in the practice of domestic healthcare, there is also a negative attitude and wariness based on the uncertainty and ambiguity of such prospects.

Healthcare digitalization in Russia started in 2018 with the state program, which appointed it as one of directions of healthcare development. Subsequently, the main vectors for the development of digitalization of the Russian healthcare system were defined in more detail. According to federal project of 2019 the single digital contour in healthcare based on the unified state information system was developed, which ensured accessibility of digital services for citizens, implemented electronic document management, including telemedicine technologies, electronic doctor's appointment, electronic prescriptions etc. The healthcare system of the Russian Federation is currently moving to a new stage of digital technology implementation - system implementation, which is aimed mainly at achieving technological sovereignty in the field of healthcare. State priorities in the field of digitalization in healthcare include platformization and

creation of "digital twins", development and implementation of artificial intelligence, big data analytics, internet of medical things (IoMT) etc.

Particular importance in digital medicine is given to artificial intelligence, the main areas of application of which are prevention, diagnosis of diseases and pathological conditions at their early stages; timeliness of diagnosis and clarification; determination of treatment tactics; pharmacotherapy, selection and replacement of drugs; management of medical personnel of healthcare organizations; quality control of medical care; health management and patient navigation; medical education, etc. (Yakovlev, 2019).

Western researchers have drawn attention to a number of problems that accompany the development of AI in the healthcare sector. Among them is the fragmentation of medical data storage, which creates difficulties in obtaining it. Also, the data itself may be of poor quality and complicate the training of the algorithm. It is noted that companies sometimes do not understand the market capacity of their product, the possibilities of its use, do not insist on the implementation of their systems and do not properly inform about how their systems lead to improvements in treatment processes. Insurance companies also have little interest in the implementation of AI.

Despite this, in Russia, due to the state-funded structure of the health care system, there are more prospects for the implementation of information technologies. While, some Western companies are experiencing financial difficulties and are abandoning developments in the field of artificial intelligence, the state support for these developments in Russia stimulates leading Russian companies - Sber and Yandex to continue research. In addition to financial support, companies developing artificial intelligence in Russia have access to extensive databases for training their algorithms.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

The main problem in digitalization of healthcare system in Russia which still is not solved is the lack of unity in the Russian digital healthcare system, which manifests itself at different levels and hinders the effective use of informatization as a tool for improving the quality of medical care in the country. Nevertheless the development of AI technologies within the Russian healthcare system is preferable, since due to centralization it eliminates certain market risks associated with the collection of primary data and the final implementation of the product in medical organizations.

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